

CORRELATION BETWEEN STUDENTS GRADES IN HOME ECONOMICS IN WAEC AND NECO EXAMINATIONS IN 2003/2004 AND 2004/2005 ACADEMIC SESSIONS

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Abstract

WAEC and NECO are the two bodies that examine Senior Secondary School (SSS) students performance in subjects offered at SSS level in Nigeria. Most people (parents, teachers and students) believe that NECO is cheaper to pass than WAEC. This research study is to investigate the performance of students in home economics in both NECO and WAEC in 2003/2004 and 2004/2005 academic sessions. In order to achieve this ten secondary schools were selected in Ondo West Local Government Area. This comprised of four mixed private, four mixed public and two girls public schools that offer home economics at SSS level and have presented candidates for WAEC and NECO for at least the past three sessions. Historical research design through documentation was used for the collection of records and information needed for the research. In analysing the grades Pearson's r correlation relationship was used. Result showed that there was a negligible relationship between students performance in the two examinations for the two academic sessions, which means there was little or no difference in the students' performance. It is concluded that NECO and WAEC are true tests of students' abilities and students can sit for the two examinations at the end of SSS studies. Recommendations were made to help students perform better in future examinations.

Introduction

Public (external) examinations have played a major role throughout the history of modern education in Africa. According to Kellaghan and Greaney (2003) they "serve a number of functions the most important of which is to select students for successive levels in the education system".

The West African Examination council (WAEC) a multi-national examining body embracing the Gambia, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria and Sierra Leone conducts such examinations as are determined by the national government of each member state. "In Nigeria the council conducts the West African School Certificate Examination, the General Certificate of Education examination mainly at the ordinary level and sparingly at the advanced levels, the Royal society of Arts Examination, the city and Guilds, the National Common Entrance Examination to Federal Secondary schools and other state secondary schools" (<http://www.online.nigeria>.)

The National Examination Council (NECO) with headquarters in Minna, Niger State was established in January 1998 as a result of a chain of recommendations of Sogbetun. Commission (1977), the Angulu panel (1982), the Osiyale committee (1993) and the Etsu Nupe Panel. The Examination Council was established to relieve WAEC of some of its obvious burdens (<http://www.onlinenigeria>.) NECO like WAEC also conduct examination for private and public senior secondary school students (known as NECO/GCE and NECO/SSCE respectively).

Home Economics is one of the subjects examined for senior secondary school students by the two examining bodies. Many factors affect and or determine students performance. Backman (1995) opined that parent's educational level, parents occupational income, family health conditions and feeling of insecurity are some of the factors that influence or inhibit good performance of students. Derville (1982) said that poor health is an inhibiting factor to learning and successful performance in schools.

Moor (1996) is of the view that children from peaceful and happy homes perform well in school. He said that children from unhappy and broken homes perform less well. Deville (1982) said "conditions such

as divorce, drunkenness and violent quarreling among parents may cause children to be upset that they are unable to concentrate in their work at school”.

Elkins (1994) stressed that between the ages of 14 and 16 males and females spend a great deal of time not only thinking about themselves but also imagine how they appear to other people around them. He said that at this age they want to show themselves approved by their mates in the school, thereby devoting little or no time to their academic work. This will tell on their performance in the school.

Flang (1989) using national representatives sample indicated that girls performed as well or slightly better than boys when tested on measure of abstract reasoning, reading, comprehension and creativity. Sution (1995) opined that school facilities such as the size of the home economics laboratory, amount of laboratory equipment have significant effect on students' performance in home economics. Grant and Oar (1989) are strongly against the current system of education and attribute the poor performance of students in examination to the system of education. They said there is need for the teachers to have the knowledge of their students and their individual differences, as this will enhance interaction and promote learning which will lead to a brilliant performance in their examination.

Other factors include peer and parental influence, heritage of the family, mental status, home environment, school environment, availability of library facilities (number and types of books present), amount of rewards and recognition students receive from parents, staff strength (quantity and quality) in school, examination malpractices e.t.c.

Statement of the Problem

The question still remains, of the 2 examinations, NECO and WAEC, which is easier and more difficult. Most people (parents, teachers and students) believe that NECO is cheaper to pass than WAEC. It is against the backdrop that this study sets out to correlate the scores of students in the two exams.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to investigate:

- the performance of students in home-economics in both NECO and WAEC in 2003/2004 and 2004/2005 academic sessions.
- if students performance is the same or not in the two examinations
- if students perform better in 2004/2005 than 2003/2004.

Research Design

The researcher used historical research design through documentation in the collection of document, records and information needed for this study. WAEC and NECO results for 2003/2004 and 2004/2005 sessions of Home Economics students were collected from the Examination officer in each of the ten randomly selected secondary schools.

Population and Sample Selection

For the purpose of this study, the target population comprised of SSS 3 home economics students in Ondo West Local Government of Ondo State.

Ten Secondary Schools were randomly selected for the study. The schools selected were those that offer Home Economics at Senior Secondary school level and have been presenting candidates for WAEC and NECO for at least the past two years.

The schools were four mixed private, four mixed public and two girls all in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Research Instrument

The main instrument used were the grades obtained in WAEC and NECO examination in home economics for 2003/2004 and 2004/2005 academic sessions. The grades were extracted from the results collected from the examination officer in each school. Both WAEC and NECO have their grades represented as A1, B2, B3, C4, C5, C6, D7, E8, F9.

Method of data analysis

Pearson's product moment correlation coefficients of the students' scores were calculated to determine students performance in home economics.

The formular of Pearson's correlation is

$$r = \frac{N\sum xY - \sum x\sum Y}{(\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2)(\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)^{1/2}}$$

The rule of thumb for r is

r ranges from -1 through 0 to +1

+0.00	to +0.19	=	Negligible
+0.20	to +0.39	=	Low
+0.40	to +0.59	=	Moderate
+0.60	to +0.79	=	Substantial / Appreciable
+0.80	to +0.99	=	High
When r is	+ 1	=	Perfect relationship.

Result and Discussion

Data Analysis

This chapter involves the data analysis to show the performance of students in home economics for the year 2003/2004 and 2004/2005 academic sessions in both NECO and WAEC.

Table 1: Correlation Between Distinction Scores of Students In NECO and WAEC 2003/2004

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC x NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
7	6	42	49	36
7	6	42	49	36
5	7	35	25	49
10	4	40	100	16
6	8	48	36	64
4	5	20	16	25
7	5	35	49	25
6	10	60	36	100
8	6	48	64	36
5	7	35	25	49
$\sum X = 65$	$\sum Y = 64$	$\sum XY = 405$	$\sum X^2 = 449$	$\sum Y^2 = 436$

$$r = \frac{N\sum Y - \sum X\sum Y}{(\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2)(\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)^{1/2}}$$

N = 2 = WAEC and NECO

X = Scores on WAEC

$\sum X = 65$, $\sum XY = 405$

$\sum Y = 64$, $\sum X^2 = 449$, $\sum Y^2 = 436$.

$r = (2 \times 405) - (65 \times 64)$

$(2 \times 449 - (65)^2)(2 \times 436 - (64)^2)^{1/2}$

$r = -0.000624$

The above table shows the correlation between student's performance in NECO and WAEC examination for the year 2003/2004. In the calculation, we can see that we have a negligible relationship when we look at the students who score distinction in the exams. This means there is little or no difference in the distinction scores of students in WAEC and NECO examination in 2003/2004 academic session.

Table II: Correlation Between Credit Scores of Students in NECO and WAEC 2003/2004

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC X NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
3	7	21	9	49
3	3	9	9	9
4	2	8	16	4
1	2	2	1	4
2	0	0	4	0
0	1	0	0	1
4	1	4	16	1
7	5	35	49	25
0	2	0	0	4
1	1	1	1	1
$\Sigma X = 25$	$\Sigma Y = 24$	$\Sigma XY = 80$	$\Sigma X^2 = 103$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 98$

$r = -0.005526$

The second table shows the correlation between students' performance in NECO and WAEC for the year 2003/2004. It shows the results of students that scored credit in the exams. The correlation coefficient (r) 0.005526 means there is a slight difference in the scores of the students because a negligible relationship is shown.

Table III: Correlation Between Pass Scores of Students in NECO and WAEC 2003/2004

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC and NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
0	1	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	4	0
1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	0
2	2	4	4	4
$\Sigma X = 7$	$\Sigma Y = 4$	$\Sigma XY = 4$	$\Sigma X^2 = 11$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 6$

$r = -0.19$

The above table also shows that $r = -0.19$ which means that there is a negligible correlation among the pass scores in NECO and WAEC of 2003/2004 academic session. This means there is a little difference among the performance of the students in the exams.

Table IV: Correlation Between Distinction Scores of Students In NECO and WAEC 2004/2005

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC x NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
6	9	54	36	81
5	4	20	25	16
6	6	36	36	36
3	3	9	9	9
6	10	60	36	100
4	6	24	16	36
4	4	16	16	16
9	7	63	81	49
4	4	16	16	16
5	3	15	25	9
$\Sigma X = 52$	$\Sigma Y = 56$	$\Sigma XY = 313$	$\Sigma X^2 = 216$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 368$

$$r = -0.00091$$

This table shows that there is a negligible relationship in the distinction result of students in home economics. This means 2004/2005 NEC and WAEC distinction performance of students is nearly the same.

Table V: Correlation between Credit Scores of Students in NECO and WAEC 2004/2005

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC x NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
6	5	30	36	25
5	3	15	25	9
6	3	18	36	9
3	1	3	9	1
6	4	24	36	16
2	5	10	4	25
4	4	16	16	16
9	7	63	81	49
4	4	16	16	16
5	3	15	25	15
$\Sigma X = 50$	$\Sigma Y = 39$	$\Sigma XY = 210$	$\Sigma X^2 = 284$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 172$

$$r = -0.001382$$

The above table shows the calculation of student's performance in NECO and WAEC 2004/2005. There is a negligible relationship between home economics performance of students who scored credit grades.

Table VI: Correlation Between Pass Scores of Students in NECO and WAEC 2004/2005

WAEC X	NECO Y	WAEC x NECO XY	(WAEC) ² X ²	(NECO) ² Y ²
2	2	4	4	4
2	0	0	4	0
1	2	2	1	4
0	2	0	0	4
2	2	4	4	4
2	2	2	4	0
0	1	0	0	1
2	1	2	4	1
1	1	1	1	1
$\Sigma X = 12$	$\Sigma Y = 14$	$\Sigma XY = 15$	$\Sigma X^2 = 72$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 24$

$$r = -1.13$$

Table VI above shows the correlation of the students' performance who scored or were graded pass in 2004/2005 NECO and WAEC results. The students' performance is almost the same in the previous year 2003/2004 which is a perfect relationship. This means there is a slight improvement in the performance of students who passed in 2004/2005.

Conclusion

This study revealed that students' performance in the two academic sessions (2003/2004 and 2004/2005) in both NECO and WAEC examinations was nearly the same. The exams are true tests of the ability of students as they scored almost the same grades in the two exams in the two sessions. Students performance is good in home economics as most of them had distinction scores followed by credit and very few had pass scores (as seen in Tables I – VI). Table VI shows that there is a slight improvement in the performance of students who passed in 2004/2005. If the factors affecting teaching and learning processes of home economics are improved upon, the problems faced by the students could be identified and lasting solutions can be found to them.

Recommendations

In the light of the above; The Researcher makes the following recommendations:

- Home Economics is a practical oriented subject, therefore students should take their practical classes seriously to enhance excellent performance.
- Teachers should have good relationships with their students so that the latter will be able to express their personal or academic problems, this will help to improve their performance.
- Teachers should encourage the students and stimulate their interests to boost their performance.
- Students should make use of the library to get more information than what they are taught in the classrooms.
- Teachers should obtain more knowledge by attending seminars, symposia and workshops to broaden their views and improve students performance.
- Parents should encourage their children/wards by providing them money for practicals and necessary textbooks.
- Government should provide funds to equip home economics laboratories.
- Further investigations should be carried out on the performance of students in home economics in continuous assessment and internal examinations.

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